

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15348940

Enhancing Conventional Building Project Delivery through Sustainable Eco-Friendly Materials: A Study of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

Oduali, Nheomachi Faith¹ & Prof. E.C. Ubani²

¹Department of Quantity Surveying,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

²Department of Project Management Technology,
Federal University of Technology Owerri, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The construction industry is a major contributor to environmental degradation, primarily due to the extensive use of conventional building materials like cement, asbestos, and synthetic paints. As urbanization and housing demand escalate in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, there is an urgent need to adopt sustainable eco-friendly building materials (SEBM) to mitigate environmental impacts and improve project performance. This study evaluates the influence of SEBM on conventional building project (CBP) performance and examines the correlation between the environmental, economic, and social benefits of SEBM integration. A survey was conducted among key construction professionals in Port Harcourt using structured questionnaires, and the results were analyzed with Pearson correlation analysis. The findings indicate a strong positive relationship between the use of SEBM and enhanced project performance, including improved cost efficiency, durability, environmental protection, and social well-being. Renewable resources and recycled materials showed the highest correlation with project performance. The study concludes that a strategic shift towards SEBM is essential for achieving sustainable urban development in Rivers State. Recommendations include government policy reforms, public awareness initiatives, and the promotion of local sustainable materials.

Keywords: Sustainable Materials, Conventional Building, Eco-friendly Construction, Project Performance, Port Harcourt, Environmental Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

The world today is facing critical environmental challenges driven largely by industrial activities and unsustainable construction practices. In developing countries like Nigeria, the building industry heavily relies on conventional materials that not only deplete natural resources but also exacerbate greenhouse gas emissions and pollution (Chukwu et al., 2019). Port Harcourt, known for its rapid urban growth, is witnessing an increased demand for housing and infrastructure, leading to heightened environmental degradation.

Sustainable construction, according to the Environmental Protection Agency, is the process of designing buildings and employing resource and environmentally-conscious methods at every stage of a building's lifecycle, including design, construction, operation, maintenance, renovation, and deconstruction (P. C. Nwogu & Emedosi, 2024). Among other design considerations for improved sustainable performance, sustainable building construction incorporates energy-saving strategies such as low emissivity glass, green roof technology, solar energy cells, energy-efficient air conditioning systems, sun shading devices, building space planning and orientation. (Qian et al. 2015). Sustainable or green building focuses on the interaction between the structure and the environment, limiting negative effects on the environment, health risks, energy use, and natural resource consumption.

(mayhoub et al. 2020). According to Prutha Patel, (2021) because of the increase in population, the adoption of sustainable structures is required and the construction industry places high priority on the construction of sustainable buildings. He is also of the opinion that due to the huge urbanization activities, lots of environmental issues are originating in the sense that the recent advanced technology and facilities consume more energy which directly or indirectly impact on the environment. The building construction industry also consume enormous amounts of energy and raw materials, as well as releases a significant amount of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere, all of which have a negative impact on human health and cause climate change (Nwogu & Emedosi, 2024). The only way to lessen the impact of pollution is for the building sector to shift toward sustainable building practices (Patel et al, 2021).

Nduka and Ogunsanmi (2015) study on the Adoptability of Green Building Practices in Construction Projects in Nigeria states that to ensure awareness and knowledge of the practice, professional organizations should teach and educate their members on green or sustainable concepts. Professionals must participate in training programs, seminars, and conferences to advance their understanding of sustainable design, the availability of sustainable building materials, and construction processes and procedures. Adopting a green or sustainable design concept aims to minimize energy consumption, operating and maintenance costs, boost occupant productivity and comfort, minimize waste and pollution, and increase building and component durability and adaptability. The emphasis on green or sustainable concept should be adopted at the design, planning, and construction stages of the project. Sustainable eco-friendly building materials (SEBM) offer a promising alternative. Materials like bamboo, straw bales, reclaimed wood, and rammed earth possess lower environmental footprints, promote energy efficiency, and enhance indoor health quality (Amal & Halil, 2017). This study focuses on investigating the role of SEBM in improving conventional building project (CBP) performance in Port Harcourt. By evaluating the environmental, economic, and social benefits of integrating these materials, this research aims to encourage stakeholders to embrace sustainable construction practices for a healthier built environment.

Problem Statement

Port Harcourt's construction industry continues to rely heavily on conventional materials that negatively impact the environment. Studies indicate that 65% of landfill waste, 70% of energy consumption, and a significant portion of greenhouse gas emissions are linked to the building sector (Usman et al., 2014). The scarcity of fully sustainable buildings in Rivers State reflects the industry's slow adoption of eco-friendly alternatives. This situation demands urgent attention to integrate sustainable materials that can enhance project performance while protecting the environment.

Aim of the study

The aim of this study is to evaluate the influence of sustainable eco-friendly building materials (SEBM) on the performance of conventional building projects (CBP).

Objectives of the study

1. To evaluate the influence of sustainable eco-friendly building materials (SEBM) on the performance of conventional building projects (CBP).
2. To correlate the environmental, economic, and social benefits of SEBM integration with the performance level of CBP.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Building materials refer to a blend of naturally sourced or artificially produced minerals or compositions employed in constructing structures. These materials encompass a variety of substances like concrete, sand, granite, gravel, fabricated steel, foundational steel, sandcrete blocks, fired bricks, cement blocks, roofing materials, among others. (Opara, 1999). The three main principles of construction materials are resources, contamination, and execution (Berge, 2010). Any building material uses resources when it is being produced, which includes all of the raw materials and energies used from the time of extraction to the time of removal. As was said above, contamination refers to any harmful emissions that result from the production of the material, products used to clean and maintain the material, off-gassing from materials during their lifetime, and final burning or landfilling. A sustainable or environmentally friendly material is one that is both eco-friendly and possesses traits such as renewability, biodegradability, and recyclability. As outlined by Attmann

(2019), these materials fall into three main categories: nanomaterials (such as nano-carbon tubing), biomaterials (organic materials like polyurethane, carbon, and straw), and smart materials (including carbon fiber). However, Baumann, & Bragd, (2012) assessed that the disarray regarding the meaning of green materials is still present. The three R's (re-use, recycle, and reduce) should be considered while picking the best building materials, according to (Kelly and Hunter, 2019). Building materials that are typically considered to be "green" include things like bamboo, due to its rapid growth, straw, responsibly harvested wood from well-managed forests, biological blocks, dimension stone, reused stone, recycled metal, and similar non-toxic, renewable, recyclable, and/or reusable materials (Shittu, 2014).

Enhancing safety and wellness is important not only from a human perspective to reduce receivers' anxiety, but also as a means of ensuring the success and sustainability of the buildings, as well as their advancement over a longer and better term. When we plan or carry out a development project, we should keep in mind a strong concern for nature protection. We should take into account how circuits of matter and energy change, which becomes necessary and only practical if we fully embrace and take into account ecological enactment on the unique preservation of nature (Cazacu, 2015). Development's negative impact on the environment is mostly manifested in excessive energy consumption and CO₂ emissions, which result in global warming, water pollution, the production of solid waste, noise, and dust (Georgescu, 2015). Reusing building materials is becoming more popular as a way to reduce the environmental impact of the construction industry (Sarvesh & Chouhan, 2013). Despite the fact that projects are carried out on a few different levels and are wisely examined based on the financial results, the actual environmental implications are rarely taken into consideration (Sarvesh & Chouhan, 2013).

The environmental impact of a building as a whole will be significantly reduced by recycling these materials (Sarvesh & Chouhan, 2013). For energy efficiency, sustainability, and durability, green buildings use materials that are currently available (Akshay et al, 2015). Utilizing lime in construction aids in sequestering carbon rather than releasing it, thereby mitigating adverse environmental impacts. Lime serves as a sustainable building material, reducing indoor temperatures by 5°C to 4°C compared to concrete during plastering. (Ashish, 2012). Green construction materials reduce climatic effects to create effective, sustainable structures and, in addition, lower pollution levels that contribute to resource depletion, greenhouse gas emissions, soil contamination, ozone depletion, and health risks. There is a trend to use green building materials as a result for a better tomorrow and a healthy existence for future generations (Gupta, 2016). By integrating these materials into construction projects, green structural materials and products help protect dwindling non-sustainable resources and lessen the environmental impacts associated with the extraction, transportation, handling, manufacturing, installation, recycling, reuse, and disposal of source materials in the construction industry (Geeta et al., 2014). Research indicates that native materials including stone, grasses, mud, cow dung, bamboo, leaves, and reeds, among others, were employed in constructing diverse structures in Nigeria.

Despite the fact that these materials are easily accessible in large quantities, their use has decreased as a result of people's preference for imported building materials, which are produced carelessly and at a higher cost as a result of this (Odeyale & Adegunle, 2008). Living in brick, stone, or timber structures is thought to indicate extreme poverty, which has led to a dislike of these green building materials. Our desire for civilized structures without considering our history has also done little to help us view things critically or advance our domestic building materials rather than looking for materials from abroad (Odeyale & Adegunle, 2008). In Nigeria, there are abundant supplies of laterite, clay, lime, stone, timber, agro-industrial waste, glass sand, and bitumen in their normal or regular states, which helps to meet the demand for using these green building materials for construction purposes (Kayode & Olusegun, 2013). According to investigations, these materials have been found to be useful in the building construction sector (Kayode & Olusegun, 2013).

It was emphasized that the difficulty in providing low-income people with housing through their own efforts was due to the higher cost of the building materials, which can be traced to high rates of imported materials used for development that have drawn in much expense in comparison to the indigenous building materials (Kayode & Olusegun, 2013). If the government provided genuine information and comfort to the Nigerian residents, a variety of alternative building materials may meet their needs and those of the imported materials (Kayode & Olusegun, 2013). According to Amal

and Halil (2017), the majority of buildings in Northern Nigeria are still constructed using sustainable, traditional materials and methods like bamboo and wood. By using an easier construction process, less expensive transportation, and fewer economic demands, green building materials, also known as sustainable traditional building materials, reduce the cost of the overall construction.

Sustainable, renewable, affordable, and widely accessible green building materials will improve energy efficiency, promote sustainability, and lower construction costs when used in modern building approaches (Amal & Halil, 2017). The advancement and adoption of modernization and innovation to comply with contemporary building standards and lifestyle requirements present a challenge to the viability of green building materials. However, the growing awareness of green building practices enables the utilization of such materials by leveraging locally available resources that align with the specific needs and conditions of the locality, offering an affordable solution (Amal & Halil, 2017).

Building materials are one of the main resources needed to construct a building from the foundation to the finishing level. The cost of construction is directly related to the type of building materials employed to erect the project. Using sustainable or green building materials such as recycled materials, sustainable wood, and low emitting materials is very advantageous in the long run because they do not harm the environment during their manufacturing, usage, or disposal and are easily recyclable (Blade, 2023). Green home construction dramatically lowers carbon emissions and uses less energy, which results in lower energy costs. In contrast to a normal construction, a green building requires particular systems and materials to adapt sustainability (Sheth, 2016). Ecologically sustainable materials should be chosen, according to the Green Building Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment (GRIHA). Environmentally friendly materials typically incorporate a substantial amount of recycled content, utilize rapidly renewable resources, and exhibit low emission potential. Sustainable eco-friendly materials that are used for building construction purposes can be grouped into four categories which includes;

- Renewable resources.
- Recycled materials.
- Earthen materials
- Other sustainable options.

Renewable resources includes but not limited to the following;

1. Bamboo
2. Straw bales
3. Timber
4. Solar shingles

Bamboo: Bamboo, a type of plant, can regenerate within approximately 3–5 years. When not subjected to chemical processing, it is entirely biodegradable, possesses antimicrobial properties, and is environmentally friendly. Its axially flowing fibers are what give it its tremendous strength (Giovanni, 2021). Bamboo is one of the building materials that is becoming more and more popular. For example, in addition to its traditional uses as scaffolding and support, bamboo is now being proposed as a replacement for steel reinforcement in short beams and columns.

Straw Bales: Straw bales serve as highly effective insulation material, similar to wool, commonly installed in ceilings, attics, and walls to maintain consistent temperatures. Straw, being a renewable resource, can be harvested and replanted with minimal environmental impact. Additionally, farmers often supply straw material by repurposing it from burning off after harvest. Sarath (2012) suggests that repurposing this waste byproduct into compressed ceiling and wall panels ensures the preservation of its carbon content in an eco-friendly manner, preventing the release of embodied carbon into the environment upon destruction, thereby reducing carbon emissions. From material acquisition to energy efficiency, straw bale stands as a sustainable building material utilized in eco-friendly construction, frequently compressed and crafted into insulated cladding panels for homes.

Timber: Timber is a renewable sustainable building material, it has a low carbon footprint compared to many other building materials (Peuhkuri et al, 2019). He is of the opinion that trees naturally absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere as they grow, the carbon absorbed remains stored in the timber even after it is harvested and used in construction, helping to mitigate the impacts of greenhouse gas emissions.

Solar energy: Solar energy systems such as solar panels, are often considered sustainable building materials due to their ability to harness renewable energy from the sun. (Renewable Energy World, 2021). With advancing technology and increasingly appealing designs, solar panels are becoming more prevalent on roofs and in yards. Homes can opt for solar panel tiles or mounted structures to decrease their dependence on nonrenewable energy sources. In conclusion, solar energy is a sustainable building material that offers several environmental and economic benefits. It is renewable, cost-saving, and has ability to increase resilience to power outages.

Recycled materials include but not limited to the following:

1. Reclaimed wood
2. Recycled plastic
3. Recycled steel
4. Fly ash
5. Demolition waste

Reclaimed wood: This is an environmentally sustainable building material that offers several advantages over newly harvested timber. It is sourced from old buildings, bridges, warehouses, and other structures. Using reclaimed wood helps reduce the demand for new timber, which can help preserve forests and biodiversity (Smith, 2019). Using reclaimed wood can help reduce waste. Rather than sending old timber to landfills, it is repurposed for use in new construction projects. This helps conserve landfill space and reduce the environmental impact of waste disposal (Johnson, 2020).

Recycled plastic: According to Barbulianno, (2020) plastic items can take up to 1000 years to decompose, whereas the plastic bags we use every day take 10–20 years and plastic bottles take 450 years. It's time to begin cleaning up our planet and reusing all the plastic that we have let to float freely in our parks, oceans, and residences. Barbulianno (2020) claims that recycled plastic reduces greenhouse gas emissions by 95% when compared to concrete blocks. Recycled plastic is a strong, long-lasting material that is excellent at retaining sound.

Recycled steel: This is produced from scrap steel, which can include old cars, appliances and demolished buildings. Using recycled steel in construction helps to reduce the need for virgin steel production, which is energy intensive and contributes to greenhouse gas emissions (Steel Recycling Institute, 2020). According to the Steel Recycling Institute, recycling steel can save up to 74% of the energy required to produce steel from raw materials. By using recycled steel in construction projects, builders can help conserve natural resources, reduce energy consumption, and minimize waste.

Fly Ash: According to Marcelle, (2023). Fly ash is a byproduct of coal combustion made up of the tiny fragments of fuel that have been burned and are expelled with the flue gases from coal-fired boilers. Fly ash is a versatile substance that may be used for a variety of tasks. Depending on the conditions in the area, it can be utilized in various ways for different products. In concrete, fly ash is used to substitute Portland cement to a maximum of 30% by mass, while larger percentages may be utilized in some circumstances. In certain cases, fly ash improves the durability, chemical resistance, and final strength of concrete. Fly ash has the potential to substitute a portion of the cement and sand in concrete, enhancing the workability of fresh concrete, reducing heat during hydration, improving impermeability, and bolstering resistance to sulfate attack. Fly ash in concrete can be used when its properties lie in certain limits as of concrete but classification by particle size and control of the unburned coal greatly enhances the beneficial effects of the fly ash.

Demolition waste: this refers to the materials that are generated from the demolition of buildings and structures, including concrete, wood metals, and other materials. Instead of sending these materials to the landfills, they can be recycled and reused in construction projects, which helps conserve natural resources and reduce waste by reducing the demand for virgin materials (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2021).

Earthen materials includes but not limited to the following;

1. Rammed earth
2. Cob
3. Stone
4. Bricks
5. Lime

Rammed earth: This is a sustainable building material that is made by compacting a mixture of earth, gravel, sand and clay between forms to create solid walls. Rammed earth construction offers

several environment benefit. Its low environmental impact, durability thermal mass properties, and non-toxic nature make it an attractive option for sustainable construction (Varges, 2019). Rammed earth walls have a long lifespan and are durable, requiring minimal maintenance over time.

Cob: Clay, sand, straw, and water are combined to create a cob, cob is a material that is malleable and flexible enough to allow for the creation of intricate and lovely structures. It is as durable as concrete after drying. Cob store and transfer heat, it is completely natural, locally sourced, renewable, and non-toxic (Rima, 2019). He is also of the opinion that due to the impermeable nature of walls and the constant discharge of gases from artificial paints, plasters, and other building materials, conventional buildings are plagued with indoor air pollution but because cob is a permeable material that breathes via its tiny pores to keep the air clear and fresh, cob houses do not have these issues. They are also damp-free. Living in a cob house could dramatically enhance your quality of life if you have indoor allergies since it gets rid of the chemicals that might be the cause. Because of its capacity to absorb sunlight and warm the structure throughout the day, as well as its ability to cool and reflect this into a hot, humid building throughout the summer, a cob house does not require supplementary heating or cooling (Kuru, 2017).

Stone: Stone is a naturally occurring substance in the earth that may be used for both construction and home furnishings like countertops and titles, according to Klemm (2016). When utilized in construction projects, stone produces little to no waste and is both long-lasting and low-maintenance. It often doesn't require factory manufacture because it is a naturally occurring material, reducing CO₂ emissions.

Bricks: Brick made from earth-derived clay and water is a natural material that is entirely recyclable and environmentally friendly. When disposed of in a landfill, it does not emit any harmful chemicals. Clay bricks are energy-efficient, helping to keep homes cooler in the summer and retain warmth for extended periods during the winter. (Torsten, 2021).

Lime: According to Eco House Store, Lime mortar is made from a mixture of lime, sand, and water. These resources are inexpensive to use in building because they are plentiful and widely accessible. Lime mortar is a more environmentally friendly option than cement mortar, which is manufactured of Portland cement. Due to the use of fossil fuels in its production, Portland cement greatly increases carbon dioxide emissions. Lime mortar, on the other hand, is formed of organic resources and has a smaller carbon footprint. Additionally, lime mortar production uses a lot less energy than current cement production, which entails high temperatures (1300°C–1450°C) and large atmospheric carbon dioxide emissions. Lime production, on the other hand, typically requires lower temperatures (between 954°C and 1066 °C) and is therefore more environmentally friendly.

Other sustainable options includes but not limited to the following;

1. Cork
2. Sheep wool
3. Hempcrete
4. Rice husk
5. Cow dung

Cork: Cork, derived from the cork oak tree, stands out as an exceptionally sustainable and environmentally friendly material. It boasts resilience against moisture and liquids, along with the ability to dampen vibrations effectively. Moreover, it excels in noise absorption, rendering it ideal for insulation purposes. Its impressive shock-absorbing capabilities make it suitable for sub-flooring, while its inherent fire resistance, particularly when untreated, enhances its value as a thermal insulator that doesn't emit harmful gases when burned. And even more, being nearly impervious, this material does not absorb water or rot (Knapic et al, 2016).

Sheep's Wool: Sheep's wool stands as a wholly natural and eco-friendly material, capable of rapid regeneration. Renowned for its use in crafting warm blankets and sweaters, wool's fibers form countless small air pockets that effectively trap air, making it an outstanding choice for home insulation. Its energy-saving properties and easy accessibility further underscore its excellence. (Bosia et al, 2015).

Hempcrete: Hempcrete comprises a blend of sand, hemp fibers, and lime, commonly utilized in construction and insulation. Notably lightweight and easy to handle, hempcrete blocks are made from hemp, a rapidly renewable resource, making them environmentally friendly (Biehl, 2019). Once dried, hempcrete exhibits no fracture lines due to its permeable, non-shrinking nature. While not as robust as

concrete, it offers resistance to pests and fire, along with effective insulation properties. Designed as a non-load-bearing glued masonry product, hemp blocks are versatile and appreciated by professionals for various construction and renovation projects, including healthy and natural insulating envelopes, partition walls, and counter-partitions. (Megan, 2021).

Rice Husk: Rice husk ash (RHA) serves two main purposes in concrete construction. Firstly, it can substitute Portland cement, effectively reducing concrete production costs. Secondly, it functions as an additive for producing high-strength concrete. It's essential to highlight that the form of RHA used in concrete is amorphous rather than crystalline, which makes it suitable for pozzolanic activity. Apart from its applications in ceramic glaze and roofing shingles, RHA finds diverse uses in construction such as in high-performance concrete, insulation, green concrete, bathroom floors, industrial flooring, waterproofing, and rehabilitation projects.

Cow Dung: Cow dung is a residual resource derived from cows, comprising undigested remnants of their consumed food that are expelled through excretion (Gupta, 2016). It is a biodegradable resource that is beneficial to us in a number of ways. Pallvika (2016) asserts that cow excrement is rich in several minerals, including salt, potassium, magnesium, and others. India has used it for thousands of years in a variety of fields. Cow dung serves a variety of purposes, including insect repellent, biogas production, building material, and rich fertilizer. Minerals including potassium, magnesium, and phosphorus, which serve as good binders, are abundant in cow dung. Additionally, it makes the soil's texture better and aids with moisture retention. In India's rural dwellings, a paste made of cow dung and mud is occasionally placed to the walls and floors to create a water-resistant coating that prevents heat from entering the residence. The fibers in the dung also aid in producing a fine and smooth floor surface, as well as preventing floor cracking and improving plaster's insulating capabilities. It is also an eco-friendly, health-friendly, and mosquito repellent. It possesses anti-thermal and anti-radioactive qualities that provide a barrier for protection from dangerous radiations (magudeaswaran 2018). The combination of cow dung, water, mud, and air, according to Barman research, released serotonin, a hormone also known as a happy hormone and responsible for fostering a positive environment. The building sector is responsible for over 40% of global energy use and nearly 30% of greenhouse gas emissions (Yudelson, 2017). Integrating SEBM in construction projects offers numerous benefits:

- **Environmental Benefits:** Reduction in carbon emissions, resource conservation, and waste minimization (Patel et al., 2021).
- **Economic Benefits:** Lower operational and maintenance costs, longer material lifespan, and increased property value (Ben-Alon et al., 2019).
- **Social Benefits:** Improved indoor air quality, enhanced occupant health, and promotion of community well-being (Darko & Chan, 2018).

Moreover, green construction methods encourage passive design strategies, energy efficiency, and sustainable resource utilization, creating a ripple effect on society and future generations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a quantitative survey design, it focused on the Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State, involving key stakeholders in the construction industry, including Architects, Builders, Quantity Surveyors, and Structural Engineers, as respondents. The research instrument used in this study is the questionnaire; participants were given a survey consisting of a set of questions in line with the study objectives. The responses were analyzed using Pearson's Correlation analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section focuses on analyzing the data collected from fieldwork survey, the overarching goal of this data analysis is to provide insights that address the research questions, thereby contributing to the fulfillment of research objectives.

Table 1: Effects of Sustainable Eco-friendly Building Materials (SEBM) on the Performance of Conventional Building Projects (CBP). Correlation between SEBM (RR, OS, EM and RM) and CBP

Statistical Test		RR	OS	EM	RM	CBP
RR	Pearson correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
	N	82				
OS	Pearson correlation	0.096	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.392				
	N	82	82			
EM	Pearson correlation	0.823	0.052	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0.64			
	N	82	82	82		
RM	Pearson correlation	0.782	0.062	0.762	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.72	0.486	0.356		
	N	82	82	82	82	
CBP	Pearson correlation	0.87	0.046	0.82	0.78	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003	0.683	0	0.003	
	N	82	82	82	82	82

From Table 1, Pearson correlation between dependent variable (CBP) and independent variables (RR, OS, EM and RM) was carried out. The relationship between each independent variable and dependent variable showed correlation of 0.87 for CBP against RR, 0.82 for CBP against EM, 0.78 for CBP against RM and 0.046 for CBP against OS. The order of relationship with the dependent using the Pearson correlation as shown in Table 4.1 is RR > EM > RM > OS.

On the other hand, the relationship between independent variables showed correlation of 0.823 for RR against EM, 0.096 for RR against OS, 0.782 for RR against RM and 0.052 for OS against EM. The order according to the strength of correlation is RR vs EM > RR vs RM > RR vs OS > OS vs EM.

This indicates that the choice of renewable resources (RR) will significantly enhance the performance of conventional building projects (CBP) in Port Harcourt. The study by Ashish (2012) also showed that the use of renewable materials/resources can enhance the performance of conventional building projects. The relationship between the use of other sustainable options and the performance of CBP showed correlation coefficient 0.046 which signifies that there is no correlation between the two variables. Hence the use of materials such as rice husk cork, etc. will not enhance the performance of CBP and this can be as a result of these materials not being treated properly.

Table 2: Effects of Sustainable Eco-friendly Building Materials (SEBM) on the Performance of Conventional Building Projects (CBP). Correlation between SEBM and CBP

Statistical Test		SEBM	CBP
SEBM	Pearson correlation		1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N		82
CBP	Pearson correlation	0.86	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003	
	N	82	82

From Table 2, Pearson correlation between dependent variable (CBP) and independent variable (SEBM) was carried out. The relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable showed correlation of 0.86.

Fig 1: Developed framework for integrating sustainable eco-friendly building material (SEBM) on the performance of conventional building projects (CBP).

r = Pearson correlation coefficient of SEBM and EECS on CBP

Influence of SEBM on CBP Performance The integration of SEBM was found to positively influence project performance parameters such as cost-efficiency, durability, schedule adherence, quality, and environmental sustainability:

- Renewable Resources (RR) and Conventional Building Projects (CBP) had a correlation coefficient of 0.87.
- Earthen Materials (EM) and CBP had a correlation coefficient of 0.82.
- Recycled Materials (RM) and CBP had a correlation coefficient of 0.78
- Other Materials (OM) and CBP had a correlation coefficient of 0.046

Correlation between SEBM Benefits and CBP Environmental benefits recorded the strongest correlation with project performance ($r = 0.823$), followed by economic benefits ($r = 0.778$), while social benefits had a moderate correlation ($r = 0.206$). These findings align with prior studies (Ben-Alon et al., 2019; Darko & Chan, 2018) confirming that SEBM integration creates multi-dimensional advantages.

CONCLUSION

Materials are crucial for the construction of buildings. The mechanical strength of the building is a result of the materials' chemical, physical, and mechanical characteristics as well as an appropriate building design. The choice and use of environmentally friendly or sustainable materials should be the first step in the design of sustainable or green buildings. The findings of this study affirm that the integration of sustainable eco-friendly building materials positively impacts conventional building project performance in Port Harcourt. A strong correlation exists between SEBM benefits and project success metrics, emphasizing the urgent need for wider adoption of sustainable construction practices to ensure long-term environmental, economic, and social benefits.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Government agencies should establish mandatory frameworks for sustainable construction practices.
2. Professional bodies should organize seminars and certification programs on SEBM application.
3. The use of locally sourced sustainable materials should be encouraged to reduce costs and environmental impacts.
4. Create media campaigns to educate the public on the long-term advantages of sustainable/green buildings.

REFERENCES

- Akadiri, P. O., Chinyio, E. A., & Olomolaiye, P. O. (2012). Design of a Sustainable Building: A Conceptual Framework for Implementing Sustainability in the Building Sector.
- Amal, A., & Halil, A. (2017). Sustainable Traditional Building Materials for Affordable Housing.
- Ashish, K. P. (2012). Construction of an Eco-Friendly Building using Green Building Approach. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 3(6), 12- 24.
- Attmann, O. (2019). Green architecture-advanced materials and technologies. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Baumann, H., Boons, F. & Bragd, A. (2002). Mapping the green product development field - engineering, policy and business perspectives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 10(5),409-425.
- Ben-Alon, L., Loftness, V., & Hakkinen, T. (2019). Life-cycle assessment of sustainable building materials.
- Berge, B. (2010). The ecology of building materials. Oxford: Architectural Press.
- Biehl, Z., (2019). The Amazing world of Hemp: Hempcrete – the most sustainable building materials on earth.
- Bosia, D., Lorenzo S., Francesca, T., and Alessia, P., (2015). Sheep wool for sustainable Architecture.
- Cazacu, C. and Chițonu, G. C. (2015). Ecological criteria considering the connections between the construction, building-site and the spatial planning development. 3rd China-Romania Science and Technology Seminar (CRSTS 2018) IOP Publishing IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering 399 (2018) 012006 doi:10.1088/1757-899X/399/1/012006.
- Chukwu, O. C., Okonkwo, A. C., & Udoh, O. E. (2019). Sustainable Construction Practices: A Key to Mitigating Environmental Degradation.
- Darko, A., & Chan, A. P. C. (2018). Strategies to Promote Green Building Technologies Adoption in Developing Countries.
- Geeta, M., Mehta, A. & Sharma, B. (2014). Selection of Materials for Green Construction.
- Geng, X., Chen, J., & Dong, Y. (2017). Green Building in the Urban Context.
- Georgescu, D. & Apostu A., (2015). The impact of reinforced concrete constructions on the environment. Technical University of Civil Engineering, <http://civile.utcb.ro/metex/etapa33.pdf>.
- Giovanni, V., (2021). Why Bamboo is a sustainable building material.
- GRIHA (2010). Manual Volumn -1 Introduction to Rating System-GRIHA published by Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, Government of India, and TERI, the Energy and Resource Institute, New Delhi (2010).

- Gupta, R. (2016). Sustainable Development and Green Building. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 2 (3), 41-64.
- Johnson, M., (2020). Waste not, want not: The Environmental Benefits of Reclaimed Wood. *Environmental Conservation*, 25(4), 210-225.
- Klemm, A., and David W. (2016). Sustainability of natural stone as a construction material.
- Knapic, S., Vanda, O., Jose, S.M., and Helena, P., (2016). Cork as a building material.
- Koru, U., (2017). Benefits of building with cob. www.Koruarchitects.co.uk.
- Magudeaswaran, P., (2018). Development of Eco Brick and Contrete with the partially replacement of cow dung.
- Marcelle, P.V., (2023). Philippine Resources: Fly Ash an eco-friendly building material. www.philippine-resources.com.
- Mayhoub, G., (2020). Assessment of Green Building Materials' Attributes to Achieve Sustainable Building Facades Using AHP.
- Megan, S., (2021). Hempcrete: Creating Holistic Sustainability with plant.
- Nduka, D. O., & Ogunsanmi, O. E. (2015). The Adoptability of Green Building Practices in Construction Projects in Nigeria.
- Nwogu, P. C., & Emedosi, A. (2024). Benefits and Drivers of Green Building Projects Implementation in Nigeria. *British Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 12(2), 31–42. <https://doi.org/10.37745/bjes.2013/vol12n23142>
- Nwogu, P., & Emedosi, A. (2024). Barriers to Green Building Project Implementation and Sustainability in the Nigerian Construction Industry. In Article in *International Journal of Progressive Research in Engineering Management and Science · International Journal of progressive research in science and engineering* (vol. 5, issue 2). www.ijprse.com
- Odeyale, D. O., & Adekunle, A. E. (2008). Indigenous Building Materials and Their Suitability in Building Construction in Nigeria.
- Opara, F. E. (1999). Formulating Standards for Building Materials in Nigeria proceedings of a Seminar organized by the Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute (NBRRRI), Ota, Ogun State.
- Pallvika, K., (2016). Merdacotta: New sustainable building material made from cow dung.
- Patel A., Divya C., Patel A., Katrodiya Y., Jain A., Thakkar S. (2021). Slu-bricks - An innovative sustainable solution for solid waste management. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. [Ttps://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.09.175](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.09.175).
- Patel, P. (2021). Sustainable Buildings and Environmental Protection.
- Peuhkuri, R., and Mahapatra, K. (2019). Environmental benefits of timber in construction. In: Mahapatra, K. (Ed.), *Environmental Impact of Construction Materials and Practices* (pp.203-223). Springer, Cham.
- Qian Q.K., Chan E.H.W., Khalid A.G. (2015). Challenges in delivering green building projects: unearthing the transaction costs (TCs), *Sustainability* 7, 3615–3636
- Rima, S. A. (2019). Re-engineer cob into sustainable new building materials.
- Sarvesh P. S. & Chouhan M. S. (2013). Eco-Friendly building analysis with reused building materials. *Construction innovation*. 1(2)45-134.
- Sheth, K. N. (2016). Sustainable Building Materials Used in Green Buildings, 9 th International Conference on Engineering and Business Education (ICEBE) & 6 th International Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship (ICIE), 4(3), 135-143.
- Shittu, A. U. (2014). Assessing the Level of Stakeholders Awareness of Sustainable Design and Construction. Unpublished.
- Taleai, M. (2008). Life Cycle Assessment of Sustainable Building Materials.
- Usman A., Khamidi M. F. & Hassan T., (2018) “Sustainable building material for green building construction, conservation and refurbishing” Management in Construction Research Association (MiCRA) Postgraduate Conference.
- Yudelson, J.. (2017). the green building revolution. Washington, D.C.: Island Press.